

LARGE EDDY SIMULATION OF DUAL-FUEL SWIRL FLAMES

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Abstract

Dual-fuel combustion, where fuels of differing reactivity are injected in the combustor separately in time or space, is of interest for various applications. This study numerically investigates dual-fuel flames using Large Eddy Simulation (LES) with the Doubly-Conditioned Moment Closure (DCMC) model. Specifically, it examines a swirl flame with a liquid fuel spray of n-heptane (C_7H_{16}) in lean premixed methane/air (CH_4 /air) at premixed equivalence ratios (ϕ_{pmx}) of 0.14 and 0.56, spanning values below and above the lower flammability limit (LFL). The influence of ϕ_{pmx} on the structure of the flame is analysed in detail in both the physical space and the conditional scalar space of DCMC. The results are in reasonable agreement with experimental data concerning reaction zone location and flame shape. Further work must focus on capturing the extinction conditions.

Introduction

Global energy demand continues to rise, driven largely by the growth of emerging and developing economies. This increasing demand, coupled with concerns over climate change, public health, and energy security, necessitates the exploration of new fuel options. The transition from conventional fossil fuels to low/zero-carbon alternatives such as hydrogen, ammonia, natural gas, and methanol is a promising path toward achieving these goals. However, some of these alternative fuels are plagued by lower reactivity compared to fossil fuels and thus require the development of novel combustion strategies to ensure efficient and low-emission energy conversion.

One such strategy is dual-fuel combustion, where two fuels of varying reactivity are used together to help in the ignition of the fuel with lower reactivity. Fuels like hydrogen, ammonia, natural gas, and methanol can be used with each other [1–4], or are used in combination with traditional fossil fuels such as diesel or bio-diesel [5–9]. This approach not only enhances fuel flexibility, but also allows systems to adapt to varying environmental, economic, and fuel supply conditions. Furthermore, dual-fuel combustion opens up a broader design space to optimise both thermal efficiency and emissions reduction [10–12].

While dual-fuel has traditionally been studied in the context of reciprocating engines [13–15], there is growing interest in their application to gas turbines [2–4, 16] that involve swirl flames and the use of either gaseous or liquid fuels. Such swirl flames have been extensively studied in the past, primarily through lab-scale experiments, but more research is needed to understand staged combustor operation, where secondary fuel can reignite combustion products, and seamless gas turbine fuel switching, a critical requirement for dual fuel systems. Previous studies by Sidey et al. [17] on UCAM bluff body burners with liquid ethanol (C_2H_5OH) [18] and n-heptane (C_7H_{16}) [19] demonstrated that the interaction between liquid fuels and varying degrees of premixed CH_4 /air gaseous mixtures leads to complex flame behaviour, such as lean blow-off (LBO) and the flame morphology that cannot be easily interpolated from single-fuel cases (i.e., pure premixed gaseous fuel and pure liquid fuel cases).

Modelling dual-fuel combustion hence introduces significant challenges due to the complex interactions between the two fuels during combustion. These challenges are further compounded when one of the fuels is introduced as a liquid spray. Simultaneous evaporation, mixing, and combustion processes, particularly in turbulent flow conditions like those found in swirl

flames, result in intricate flame structures. These phenomena can lead to substantial changes in flame behaviour (lift-off, overall flame patterns) and variations in pollutant formation mechanisms. Consequently, numerical models must not only accurately capture both the liquid spray behaviour and the gaseous phase combustion, but also the subsequent interaction between them.

Conditional Moment Closure (CMC) is an advanced turbulence-chemistry interaction model [20], which is based on the transient solution of reactive species and enthalpy, conditioned on a passive scalar. It includes not only the effects of finite-rate chemistry, but also the defining elements of transport phenomena [21], including advection, dilatation, molecular diffusion, turbulent fluxes, micromixing, and differential diffusion (e.g., see [22]). CMC simulations have been applied to study spray flames in single-fuel systems. Previous work by Tyliczszak et al. [23] and Giusti & Mastorakos [24] investigated local extinction and blow-off behaviour for spray combustion of n-heptane and ethanol, respectively, using a swirl flame burner developed at the University of Cambridge (UCAM). CMC is suitable for simulations that are premixed or largely non-premixed and can be represented by either reaction progress variable or mixture fraction conditioning, respectively. The spray flames of Refs. [23, 24] are predominantly non-premixed, thus making them suitable for singly conditioned, mixture-fraction-based CMC. For general spray flames, including the dual-fuel cases, a wide range of modes, from non-premixed to pre-vaporised and premixed modes, can co-exist in the same flame [25]. Such flames require their reaction rates to be conditioned on both the mixture fraction and a reaction progress variable, thus requiring the Doubly-Conditioned Moment Closure (DCMC). DCMC has been assessed against DNS data before [26, 27] and successfully applied in the simulation of single-fuel spray flames of ethanol and n-heptane, in RANS [28] and LES [29] frameworks. It has also been applied to simulate turbulent jet ignition (TJI) in CH₄/air stratified mixtures [30].

This work extends the application of DCMC to numerically investigate the dual-fuel spray flames studied by Sidey & Mastorakos [19] experimentally. In that experiment, liquid n-heptane is combusted in combination with premixed CH₄/air. Specifically, the influence of the premixed equivalence ratio, ϕ_{pmx} , is analysed for values above and below the lower flammability limit (LFL), i.e., $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.14$ and $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$, under identical velocity conditions.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: the next section details the LES-DCMC methodology used for simulating the dual-fuel swirl spray flame. Subsequently, the numerical setup of the investigated burner is described. The findings related to swirl-flame behaviour at the two premixed CH₄/air equivalence ratios are then presented and analysed. Finally, the paper concludes with a discussion of the results and recommendations for future research directions.

Methodology

The basic concept of DCMC is the same as that of CMC, but the conditioning is done in two variables. In DCMC, any field variable can be written as a sum of conditionally filtered expectation and its corresponding sub-grid scale (SGS) fluctuations, $\phi = \overline{\phi|\eta, \zeta} + \phi''$, where $\overline{\phi|\eta, \zeta}$ is the short-form for $(\phi|\xi = \eta, c = \zeta)$ and η and ζ are the sample space variables for mixture fraction ξ and reaction progress variable c , respectively. It is then assumed that ϕ'' is small enough to be safely neglected, which is also called first-order moment closure in the CMC literature. It has to be noted that ϕ'' in DCMC is expected to be always smaller than the respective fluctuation of singly conditioned CMC since two conditioning variables are used [29]. Reactive scalars can then be calculated by transporting their conditional expectations and the Favre-filtered density function (FDF) $\tilde{p}(\eta, \zeta)$. The unconditioned or the resolved variable can be obtained by the integral,

$$\tilde{\phi} = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \overline{\phi|\eta, \zeta} \tilde{p}(\eta, \zeta) d\eta d\zeta \quad (1)$$

where the operator ($\tilde{\square}$) denotes the Favre-filtering of the flow-field variables.

In this work, the mixture fraction is defined to be $\xi = 0$ at the premixed CH_4/air mixture and $\xi = 1$ at the n-heptane fuel. The reaction progress variable is defined with the mass fraction of CO_2 , Y_{CO_2} , as

$$c(\mathbf{x}, t) = c_{\text{CO}_2}(\xi(\mathbf{x}, t), Y_{\text{CO}_2}(\mathbf{x}, t)) = \frac{Y_{\text{CO}_2}(\mathbf{x}, t) - Y_{\text{CO}_2}^0(\xi(\mathbf{x}, t))}{Y_{\text{CO}_2}^\dagger(\xi(\mathbf{x}, t)) - Y_{\text{CO}_2}^0(\xi(\mathbf{x}, t))} \quad (2)$$

where superscripts '0' and '†' corresponds to mixing line and equilibrium composition, respectively.

An Euler-Lagrangian approach is followed here, where the flow field of the continuous gas phase is solved by the LES-filtered Navier-Stokes equations and an enthalpy transport equation accounting for the presence of evaporative cooling, also employing a low-Mach number approximation. A dilute spray is assumed, such that the effect of liquid volume fraction on the LES-filtered conservation equations can be neglected. The dispersed liquid phase is modelled as Lagrangian particles that represent parcels of liquid droplets. For the sake of brevity, the corresponding equations are omitted here. The governing equations for resolved mixture fraction $\tilde{\xi}$ and its SGS variance $\tilde{\xi}''^2$, and progress variable \tilde{c} and its SGS variance \tilde{c}''^2 are [29],

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\rho} \tilde{\xi}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \tilde{\xi}) = \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} (D_t + \bar{D}) \nabla \tilde{\xi}) + \tilde{\rho} \tilde{\Pi} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \tilde{\rho} \tilde{\xi}''^2}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \tilde{\xi}''^2) &= \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} (D_t + \bar{D}) \nabla \tilde{\xi}''^2) \\ &\quad - 2\tilde{\rho} \tilde{N}_\xi + 2\tilde{\rho} (D_t + \bar{D}) \nabla \tilde{\xi} \cdot \nabla \tilde{\xi} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\rho} \tilde{c}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \tilde{c}) = \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} (D_t + \bar{D}) \nabla \tilde{c}) + \tilde{\rho} \tilde{\omega}_c^* + \tilde{\rho} \tilde{c} \tilde{\Pi} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \tilde{\rho} \tilde{c}''^2}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \tilde{c}''^2) &= \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho} (D_t + \bar{D}) \nabla \tilde{c}''^2) \\ &\quad - 2\tilde{\rho} \tilde{N}_c + 2\tilde{\rho} (D_t + \bar{D}) \nabla \tilde{c} \cdot \nabla \tilde{c} + 2\tilde{\rho} (\tilde{c} \tilde{\omega}_c^* - \tilde{c} \tilde{\omega}_c^*) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\tilde{\rho}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$, $\tilde{\Pi}$, \bar{D} and D_t are the filtered density, Favre-filtered velocity, volumetric rate of phase change per unit volume (a.k.a., evaporation term), molecular diffusivity and turbulent diffusivity, respectively. \tilde{N}_ξ and \tilde{N}_c are the scalar dissipation rate (SDR) of the mixture fraction and the reaction progress variable, respectively. Molecular diffusivity is calculated as $\bar{D} = \lambda/(\rho c_p)$, where λ is the thermal conductivity and c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure. Turbulent diffusivity is taken to be $D_t = \mu_{\text{sgs}}/(\rho S_{c_t})$, where μ_{sgs} is the turbulent viscosity and S_{c_t} is the turbulent Schmidt number with value $S_{c_t} = 0.4$. $\tilde{\omega}_c^*$ and $\tilde{c} \tilde{\omega}_c^*$ are the unconditional chemistry source term counterparts of $\tilde{\omega}_c^*|\eta, \zeta$ and $\zeta \tilde{\omega}_c^*|\eta, \zeta$, respectively, obtained using Eq. (1). As will be shown later, the DCMC solver calculates the term $\tilde{\omega}_c^*|\eta, \zeta$.

The SDRs \tilde{N}_ξ and \tilde{N}_c has resolved and SGS components, i.e., $\tilde{N} = \tilde{N}_{\text{res}} + \tilde{N}_{\text{sgs}}$. The choice of modelling for the SGS components are already discussed in detail in previous studies [29, 30], and will not be repeated here.

We consider a unity Lewis number approximation and adiabatic conditions in this work, hence the DCMC governing equations for conditional mass fractions ($Q_\alpha \equiv \widetilde{Y_\alpha|\eta, \zeta}$) and conditional enthalpy ($Q_h \equiv \widetilde{h|\eta, \zeta}$) are given as follows [29],

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial Q_\alpha}{\partial t} + \underbrace{\nabla \cdot (Q_\alpha \widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta})}_{\text{Advection}} &= \underbrace{Q_\alpha \nabla \cdot (\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta})}_{\text{Dilatation}} - \underbrace{\frac{1}{\widetilde{\rho p}} \nabla \cdot (\widetilde{\rho p} [\widetilde{\mathbf{u}} Y_\alpha|_{\eta, \zeta} - Q_\alpha \widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta}])}_{\text{Turbulent transport}} \\
&+ \underbrace{\frac{1}{\widetilde{\rho p}} \nabla \cdot (\widetilde{\rho p} D \nabla Y_\alpha|_{\eta, \zeta})}_{\text{Molecular diffusion}} \\
&+ \underbrace{N_\xi|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial^2 Q_\alpha}{\partial \eta^2}}_{\text{Scalar dissipation in } \xi} + \underbrace{2N_{\xi c}|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial^2 Q_\alpha}{\partial \eta \partial \zeta}}_{\text{Cross dissipation}} + \underbrace{N_c|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial^2 Q_\alpha}{\partial \zeta^2}}_{\text{Scalar dissipation in } c} \\
&+ \underbrace{\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_\alpha|_{\eta, \zeta}}_{\text{Chemical source}} - \underbrace{\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_c^*|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial Q_\alpha}{\partial \zeta}}_{\text{Apparent reaction rate}} \\
&+ \underbrace{(\delta_{\alpha F} - Q_\alpha) \widetilde{\Pi}|_{\eta, \zeta}}_{\text{Conditional volumetric evaporation source}} - \underbrace{S_\xi^-|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial Q_\alpha}{\partial \eta}}_{\text{Conditional evaporation source for } \xi} \\
&- \underbrace{S_c^-|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial Q_\alpha}{\partial \zeta}}_{\text{Conditional evaporation source for } c}
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial Q_h}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (Q_h \widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta}) &= Q_h \nabla \cdot (\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta}) - \frac{1}{\widetilde{\rho p}} \nabla \cdot (\widetilde{\rho p} [\widetilde{\mathbf{u}} h|_{\eta, \zeta} - Q_h \widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta}]) \\
&+ \frac{1}{\widetilde{\rho p}} \nabla \cdot (\widetilde{\rho p} a \nabla h|_{\eta, \zeta}) \\
&+ N_\xi|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial^2 Q_h}{\partial \eta^2} + 2N_{\xi c}|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial^2 Q_h}{\partial \eta \partial \zeta} + N_c|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial^2 Q_h}{\partial \zeta^2} \\
&- \widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_c^*|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial Q_h}{\partial \zeta} \\
&+ S_h|_{\eta, \zeta} - Q_h \widetilde{\Pi}|_{\eta, \zeta} - S_\xi^-|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial Q_h}{\partial \eta} - S_c^-|_{\eta, \zeta} \frac{\partial Q_h}{\partial \zeta}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where $\widetilde{\Pi}|_{\eta, \zeta}$ represents the conditional evaporation source term, while $S_h|_{\eta, \zeta}$ denotes the conditional enthalpy evaporation source. The terms $S_\xi^-|_{\eta, \zeta}$ and $S_c^-|_{\eta, \zeta}$ correspond to the conditional evaporation source terms for ξ and c , respectively. Additionally, $\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_\alpha|_{\eta, \zeta}$ signifies the conditional chemical source term. The quantities $N_\xi|_{\eta, \zeta}$, $N_c|_{\eta, \zeta}$, and $N_{\xi c}|_{\eta, \zeta}$ denote the conditional SDRs of ξ , c , and their cross-dissipation rate, respectively. The modelling approaches for these unclosed terms will be addressed later. In Eq. 8, a denotes the thermal diffusivity, which can be replaced by the molecular diffusivity D under the assumption of a unity Lewis number. As in Ref. [29, 30], we perform the following closures,

$$\widetilde{D \nabla Y_\alpha|_{\eta, \zeta}} = \bar{D} \nabla Q_\alpha \tag{9}$$

$$\widetilde{[\mathbf{u} Y_\alpha|_{\eta, \zeta} - Q_\alpha \widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta}]} = -D_t \nabla Q_\alpha \tag{10}$$

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{u}}|_{\eta, \zeta} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \tag{11}$$

and we model the FDF as $\tilde{p}(\eta, \zeta) = p_\beta(\eta; \tilde{\xi}, \tilde{\xi}''^2) \times p_\beta(\zeta; \tilde{c}, \tilde{c}''^2)$. p_β stands for a β -function, and in cases where the variance is small, it is replaced by a Kronecker δ -function.

The conditional SDR of ξ is modelled via Amplitude Mapping Closure [31]:

$$\widetilde{N_\xi|_{\eta, \zeta}} = N_0 G_\xi(\eta) \tag{12}$$

where

$$G_\xi(\eta) = \exp\left(-2 \left[\text{erf}^{-1}(2\eta - 1)\right]^2\right) \quad (13)$$

$$N_0 = \frac{\widetilde{N}_\xi}{\int_0^1 \int_0^1 G_\xi(\eta) \widetilde{p}(\eta, \zeta) d\eta d\zeta} \quad (14)$$

Similarly, for the conditional SDR of c , we have,

$$\widetilde{N}_c|\eta, \zeta = \frac{\widetilde{N}_c}{\int_0^1 \int_0^1 N_c^0(\eta, \zeta) \widetilde{p}(\eta, \zeta) d\eta d\zeta} N_c^0(\eta, \zeta) \quad (15)$$

The SDR profile, N_c^0 , shown in Fig. 1, is derived from premixed counterflow flame simulations involving n-heptane blends in a CH₄/air mixture under strained conditions. These simulations are conducted in a reactant-to-product (RtP) configuration to capture detailed SDR behaviour across the flame front. The counterflow flames are generated using the open-source chemical kinetics tool Cantera [32]. The use of RtP counterflow simulations for N_c^0 is valid under the assumption that liquid droplets vaporize upstream and mix well with the CH₄/air mixture. However, this assumption is not entirely valid due to the presence of non-premixed modes. Despite this limitation, RtP counterflow flame simulations are employed in this work to define the SDR profile.

Figure 1: N_c^0 generated from tabulated premixed counterflow flames under an RtP configuration for two premixed CH₄-air blends with n-heptane.

The apparent reaction rate is

$$\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_c^*|\eta, \zeta = \frac{1}{\partial Q_\psi / \partial \zeta} \left[\underbrace{\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_\psi|\eta, \zeta}_{\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_c|\eta, \zeta} + \underbrace{N_\xi|\eta, \zeta \frac{\partial^2 Q_\psi}{\partial \eta^2} + 2N_{\xi c}|\eta, \zeta \frac{\partial^2 Q_\psi}{\partial \eta \partial \zeta} + N_c|\eta, \zeta \frac{\partial^2 Q_\psi}{\partial \zeta^2}}_{\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_p|\eta, \zeta} \right] \quad (16)$$

which consists of mixing part $\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_p|\eta, \zeta$ and chemistry part $\widetilde{\dot{\omega}}_c|\eta, \zeta$. By the choice of the FDF, the cross-dissipation term in Eq. (7), (8), and (16) can be considered as 0.

The conditional evaporation terms are defined as follows [29]:

$$\widetilde{\Pi}|\eta, \zeta = \Pi_0 G_\pi(\eta, \zeta) \quad (17)$$

where,

$$\Pi_0 = \frac{\widetilde{\Pi}}{\int_0^1 \int_0^1 G_\pi(\eta, \zeta) \widetilde{p}(\eta, \zeta) d\eta d\zeta} \quad (18)$$

and $G_\pi(\eta, \zeta)$ is the presumed shape in the form of ridge in the scalar (η, ζ) space at the iso-contour of fuel mass fraction at saturation condition (Y_{F_s}). This is the 2D extension of the δ function implementation in the CMC simulations of Tyliczszak and Mastorakos [33] and Tyliczszak et al. [23]. Y_{F_s} is calculated by taking an average over all the droplets in the control volume:

$$\langle Y_{F_s} \rangle = \frac{\sum_i^{N_d} \dot{m}_i Y_{F_{s,i}} \theta_i}{\sum_i^{N_d} \dot{m}_i} \quad (19)$$

where $Y_{F_{s,i}}$ is the fuel mass fraction at the droplet surface, calculated from the saturation pressure at the droplet temperature. As highlighted in previous studies [24, 29, 34], the FDF must be constrained at the iso-contour $Q_F = Y_{F_s}$ to mitigate instabilities when its corresponding value approaches extremely low levels.

Similar to Eq. (17), $\widetilde{S_h|\eta, \zeta}$ can be modelled as,

$$\widetilde{S_h|\eta, \zeta} = \frac{\widetilde{S_h}}{\widetilde{\Pi}} \widetilde{\Pi|\eta, \zeta} \quad (20)$$

The conditional evaporation source terms for the mixture fraction and the progress variable are respectively,

$$\widetilde{S_\xi^-|\eta, \zeta} = (1 - \eta) \widetilde{\Pi|\eta, \zeta} \quad (21)$$

and,

$$\widetilde{S_c^-|\eta, \zeta} = \frac{1}{\partial Q_\psi / \partial \zeta} \left[\delta_{\psi F} - Q_\psi - (1 - \eta) \frac{\partial Q_\psi}{\partial \eta} \right] \widetilde{\Pi|\eta, \zeta} \quad (22)$$

The terms $\delta_{\alpha F}$ in Eq. (7) and $\delta_{\psi F}$ in the above equation are Kronecker delta functions, which are defined to take the value of 1 when their respective indices are equal and 0 otherwise.

Numerical Setup

In the experiment, n-heptane fuel is injected as a 60° hollow cone liquid spray at a mass flow rate of 0.27 g s⁻¹. The injection process is modelled using a Rossin-Rammler distribution of liquid parcels with a spread parameter of 3.0 and a Sauter Mean Diameter (SMD) of 30 μm. Figure 2(a) illustrates the schematic of the UCAM swirl flame burner. The premixed CH₄-air mixture flows through a swirler placed in the annular region, with vanes set at constant 60° vane angle. The swirler, positioned 49.6 mm upstream of the burner base, has a swirl number of 1.23, calculated using the geometric formulation outlined in Ref. [35]. Figure 2(b) shows the computational domain. The inlet velocity U_{inlet} is determined based on the premixed equivalence ratio, ϕ_{pmx} , and the global equivalence ratio (See Table 1), which is specified at a distance of 83.1 mm upstream of the burner base. A zero-gradient boundary condition is applied at the enclosing dome to effectively capture the recirculation zone, while the walls are treated as no-slip and adiabatic.

CONVERGE CFD is used as the flow solver [36]. LES with two equation $k - \epsilon$ model [37] is used for the SGS stresses. A base grid of 2 mm is used, and the region around the spray is further refined with a mesh size of 0.25 mm. The DCMC equation solver is coupled with the LES flow solver as in Ref. [30]. The domain is resolved by 302 DCMC cells in total. A reduced chemical mechanism with 44 species and 112 reactions is used based on Ref. [38].

Operator splitting is applied to Eqs. (7)-(8), with the individual terms solved following the methodologies outlined in previous studies [29, 30, 39]. For the boundary conditions in the DCMC space, n-heptane under saturation conditions at 1 atm is assigned to $\eta = 1$, while the premixed CH_4/air is assigned to $\eta = 0$. The initial solution in the DCMC space is set from a 0D-DCMC simulation. Flow statistics are collected over a duration of 100 ms.

Figure 2: (a) Schematic and (b) computational domain of the UCAM swirl flame burner.

Table 1: Flow conditions for the numerical simulation.

ϕ_{pmx}	ϕ_{global}	U_{inlet} (m s^{-1})
0.14	0.45	11.74
0.56	0.87	11.74

Results and Discussion

The flow conditions in this study closely resemble those reported in the experiments of Sidey & Mastorakos [19]. Specifically, the cases with $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.14$ and $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$ correspond to the conditions described as HP1 and HP4, respectively, in the experimental dataset. From the time averaged CFD results shown in Fig. 3, it can be seen that the flame with $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.14$ appears to be symmetric and attached to the bluff body, showing similar behaviour to that of pure n-heptane spray flame, as reported in [23, 40]. The addition of methane broadens the reaction zone significantly, as depicted in Fig. 3(g). Furthermore, the concentration of reaction products is higher in the $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$ case (Fig. 3), due to increased utilisation of the oxidiser with the higher methane content in the air stream. Additionally, the elevated presence of OH species in both the main recirculation zone (MRZ) and outer recirculation zone (ORZ) highlights the significant role of methane in the combustion process [19, 41].

The simulation results are compared with the OH-PLIF data from [19] for similar flow conditions (HP1 & HP4), as illustrated in Fig. 4. The predicted OH region intensity closely aligns with experimental observations. In Fig. 4(b), the simulation reveals a higher OH concentration within the hollow cone region, consistent with the experimental findings.

Fig. 5 compares the heat release rate (HRR) from the simulations with OH* chemiluminescence data reported by [19] for $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$. The relationship between HRR and OH* chemiluminescence is influenced by various factors, including fuel type and combustion mode (premixed or non-premixed), making it complex. However, the results indicate that OH* chemiluminescence reasonably predicts regions of high HRR.

To analyse the results in conditional space, four points were selected from the flow domain: P1 at the downstream above hollow cone, P2 near the spray injector, P3 within the shear layer,

Figure 3: Comparison of time-averaged fields between simulated cases with $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.14$ (left columns) and $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$ (right columns) for (a) Y_{CO} , (b) Y_{CO_2} , (c) Y_{H_2} , (d) $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, (e) Y_{O_2} , (f) Y_{CH_4} , (g) Y_{OH} and (h) Temperature.

Figure 4: Comparison of simulated time-averaged OH species concentration (left columns) with OH-PLIF measurements [19] (right columns) for (a) $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.14$ and (b) $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$.

and P4 in the ORZ (see Fig. 4(b)). At P1, located away from the injector, $\widetilde{N_{\xi}|\eta, \zeta}$ is low due to the effective evaporation of the spray and thorough mixing with the CH_4/air stream within the MRZ. This region is near the end of the reaction zone, resulting in low values of $\widetilde{N_c|\eta, \zeta}$. As a result, the conditional species and temperature at point P1 align with a low SDR scenario, serving as a reference for comparison. In contrast, P2, positioned close to the spray injector, exhibits high values of the conditional SDRs $\widetilde{N_{\xi}|\eta, \zeta}$ and $\widetilde{N_c|\eta, \zeta}$ (Fig. 7). These elevated SDRs

Figure 5: Comparison of heat release rate and OH* chemiluminescence [19] for $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$.

reflect significant deviations in the conditional reactive species compared to P1. At P3, located in the shear layer, $\widetilde{N_{\xi}}|\eta, \zeta$ decreases compared to P2, but $\widetilde{N_c}|\eta, \zeta$ remains high. This leads to pronounced deviations in the conditional reactive species near the global stoichiometry line, η_{st} , which corresponds to a global equivalence ratio of 1. At P4, within the ORZ, both conditional SDRs are substantially lower than at P2 and P3, resulting in conditional species and temperature profile that closely resemble those at P1. This demonstrates the influence of conditional SDRs on the reactive species distribution across different regions of the flow domain.

Figure 6: Conditional temperature, conditional mass fraction Q_{CO} and condition mass fraction $Q_{\text{CH}_2\text{O}}$ for $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$ at different points in the flow field.

The contour plots of joint-FDFs and SDRs in Fig. 7 are obtained by conditional volume averaging over all the LES cells inside a DCMC cell. As mentioned before, the joint-FDF is the product of two β -distributions (actually blend of β and δ distributions). The presumed shape of the FDF widens with increasing variance. The broad range of values in the joint-FDF at P2 indicates the high variance in both the mixture fraction ξ''^2 and the progress variable $\widetilde{c''^2}$ near the injector. At P3, the FDF shape reflects moderate variance in ξ''^2 and high variance in $\widetilde{c''^2}$.

Finally, at P4, the FDF reveals a composition dominated by a premixed CH₄/air mixture with high variance in the progress variable (i.e., high \widetilde{c}^2).

Figure 7: Conditional SDR of ξ ($\widetilde{N}_\xi|\eta, \zeta$), conditional SDR of c ($\widetilde{N}_c|\eta, \zeta$) and joint-FDF ($\widetilde{p}(\eta, \zeta)$) for $\phi_{\text{pmx}} = 0.56$ at different points in the flow field.

Conclusions

The application of LES-DCMC for dual-fuel combustion was demonstrated by simulating a flame formed in a swirl burner with n-heptane spray injection in the recirculation zone formed by the swirling annular flow of air premixed with methane at lean compositions, including leaner than the nominal lean flammability limit. The LES-DCMC results satisfactorily captured the complex flame patterns and trends observed in the experiments. The predicted flame fields were analysed and complemented by an analysis in conditional space to provide deeper insights into the flame structure and the differences between cases. This work has significant implications for fuel switching in gas turbines and can be extended to study different fuel combinations. Future work will focus on investigating blow-off behaviour and exploring additional fuel combinations, such as ethanol and hydrogen with heavier hydrocarbons.

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